

CHEMOTHERAPY OF BACTERIAL INFECTIONS. PART III, N¹-β-PHENYLETHYLSULPHANILAMIDES.*

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In order to throw light on the so-called specificity of antibacterial action of a drug to its chemical structure, and also to discover a sulphanilamide drug for use in enteric diseases, some N¹-β-phenylethylsulphanilamides have been synthesised.

A striking fact about sulphanilamide is its high curative ability in a number of resistant bacterial infections, i.e. its polyvalent action which tends to increase in specificity of the compounds obtained by proper substitution at N¹, towards one type of bacteria. It would, however, appear premature from the meagre experimental data available to propound any theory connecting the substituent group 'R' (in I) to the characteristic

bacterial morphology or ætiology of their infections, much less to determine beforehand what "R" must be, so that the product may possess any desired "specificity". In the present investigation, which was undertaken with a view to finding out an effective chemotherapeutic agent for use in enteric diseases, an attempt has been made to see whether the nature of the substituent 'R' could be correlated with the peculiar demands of these infections as evinced by their ætiological analysis. It is known (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1937, 128, 796; *Compt. rend.*, 1937, 204, 1759) that enteric bacteria strictly confine themselves to intestinal tracts which are rendered in many cases hypothermic and alkaline. Shiga organisms, besides elaborates an enterotropic endotoxin (showed by Flexner and Sonne strains) and a neurotropic endotoxin which get absorbed by the intestinal walls. From a careful analysis of the works of Kolmer and Rule (*Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. & Med.*, 1939, 40, 23) and Levaditi and Vaisman (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1938, 128, 463; 1939, 131, 33) it should be inferred that sulphonamides though possessing definite antiendotoxic and antibacterial action fail to give any favourable result against the endotoxin. It is, therefore, imperative to take into

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account this important fact in devising any therapeutic agent. In order to control the absorption of this exotoxin into the blood, and to effect a cure of Shiga infections, the enteric walls should be rendered less permeable *i.e.* the drug should be endowed in addition with vasoconstricting action. The usual vasoconstrictors being compounds of the β -phenylethylamine class, it occurred to the author that the specifying group R in (I) for Shiga infections may belong to this class. Accordingly some N^1 - β -phenylethylsulphanilamides (II, X=H, OH, OMe, NH_2 and NO_2 ; III, X=Y=OMe) have been prepared for pharmacological examination. It may be pointed

out in this connection that derivatives of phenylethylamine carboxylic acids like phenylalanine and tyrosine give active products against streptococci.

There is another important peculiarity of this group that also demands attention in this connection *viz.* the hypothermic factor (Olitzi and Avinery, *Brit. J. Exptl. Path.*, 1937, 18, 316). In order to overcome this *ac*-tetrahydro- β -naphthylamine, a unique compound combining in itself powerful vasoconstrictor action and calorising capacity has been utilised (*cf.* V).

However, as the nature of the pressor action has been normally assumed to be dependent upon the presence or liberation *in vivo* of a free amino (or imino) group in phenylethylamine, it appeared desirable also to prepare compounds having such a grouping, while being at the same time fused at N^1 -nitrogen of sulphanilamide *e.g.* (VI).

The results of the pharmacological examination of these compounds will be published in due course.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the following experiments yields of products should be taken as varying from 80 to 100 % unless explicitly stated.

*N*¹-*β*-Phenylethylacetylsulphanilamide, obtained by interacting *β*-phenylethylamine (6 g.) and freshly prepared *p*-acetylamino benzene sulphochloride (12 g.) in the usual way in presence of sodium hydroxide (20 c. c. of 2.5*N*), crystallised from alcohol in lustrous lumps, m.p. 126°. (Found: N, 8.9. C₁₆H₁₈O₂N₂S requires N, 8.81 per cent).

*N*¹-*β*-Phenylethylsulphanilamide.—The above acetyl compound (8 g.) was boiled with hydrochloric acid (10 %, 60 c. c.) under reflux for 25 minutes. The clear solution on cooling deposited glistening plates of the hydrochloride of the base, m.p. 225°. (Found: N, 9.1. C₁₄H₁₇O₂N₂ClS requires N, 8.96 per cent). The free base obtained by decomposing the above salt with ammonia crystallised from alcohol in colourless, glistening, elongated plates, m.p. 143°. (Found: N, * 10.2. C₁₄H₁₆O₂N₂S requires N, 10.15 per cent).

*N*¹-(4-Methoxy-*β*-phenylethyl)-acetylsulphanilamide, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol (charcoal) in stout prism-like crystals, m.p., 157°. (Found: N, 7.9. C₁₇H₂₀O₄N₂S requires N, 8.1 per cent).

*N*¹-(4-Methoxy-*β*-phenylethyl)-sulphanilamide.—The above acetyl compound was boiled with excess of 10% hydrochloric acid for about 1½ hours. On cooling, the solution deposited colourless plates of the hydrochloride, m.p. 218-9° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 10.5. C₁₅H₁₉O₃N₂ClS requires Cl, 10.36 per cent). The free base was obtained by treating the salt with ammonia and was purified by crystallisation from alcohol. It separated in shining thick aggregates of rods, m.p. 149°. (Found: N, 9.2. C₁₃H₁₆O₃N₂S requires N, 9.15 per cent). Refluxing the amine with concentrated hydrobromic acid solution for 3 hours and just basifying the product with ammonia, a colourless amorphous product, m.p. about 185° (decomp.), sparingly soluble in hot alcohol, was obtained. It gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 9.3. C₁₄H₁₆O₃N₂S requires N, 9.59 per cent). (The experiments with tyramine and other *β*-phenylethylamine alkaloids are reserved for a future communication).

*N*¹-(3,4-Dimethoxy-*β*-phenylethyl)-sulphanilamide.—The crude acetyl compound, obtained in the usual way, after washing was directly hydrolysed by refluxing with hydrochloric acid (10%, 100 c. c.) for 1 hour. The clear

and somewhat concentrated solution was made just alkaline with ammonia under cooling. The pale yellow product, thus obtained, was purified by twice crystallisation from 50% alcohol (charcoal) as colourless plates, m.p. 126-27°. (Found : N, 8.4. $C_{16}H_{20}O_4N_2S$ requires N, 8.33 per cent).

*N*¹-(4-Nitro- β -phenylethyl)-acetylsulphanilamide, prepared from the corresponding nitroamine by the general method, was purified by successive crystallisations from 80 % acetic acid and alcohol. It separated in shining spangles or thick plates from alcohol, m.p. 183-84°. (Found : N, 11.4. $C_{16}H_{17}O_5N_3S$ requires N, 11.57 per cent).

*N*¹-(4-Nitro- β -phenylethyl)-sulphanilamide.—The above acetyl compound was boiled with ten times of hydrochloric acid (10%) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The hydrochloride that separated on cooling decomposed at about 202° with melting. The free base obtained after treatment of the solution with ammonia, crystallised from alcohol in pale yellow prismatic needles, m.p. 207°. (Found : N, 13.1. $C_{14}H_{15}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 13.08 per cent).

*N*¹-(4-Amino- β -phenylethyl)-sulphanilamide was obtained by the reduction of the above nitro compound using tin and hydrochloric acid. (The reduction of acetyl derivative of the nitro compound was not satisfactory). A mixture of the nitro compound (5 g.), tin foil (5 g.), water (15 c.c.) and hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath till the nitro compound went into solution. After dilution with water and removal of tin as sulphide in the usual way, the solution was somewhat concentrated and just basified with ammonia. The diamine crystallised from alcohol in colourless, prismatic plates, m.p. 154-55°. (Found : N, 14.5. $C_{14}H_{17}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 14.42 per cent). It is somewhat unstable as it turns pinkish on heating in alcoholic solution. The di-acetate, m.p. 230°, separated from alcohol in silky plates or feathery needles. (Found : N, 11.4. $C_{18}H_{21}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 11.2 per cent).

*dl-N*¹-(ac-Tetrahydro- β -naphthyl)-acetylsulphanilamide, obtained from the appropriate amine and sulphochloride in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol in colourless prismatic needles or columns, m.p. 190-91°. (Found : N, 8.2. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 8.14 per cent).

*dl-N*¹-(ac-Tetrahydro- β -naphthyl)-sulphanilamide.—The above acetyl compound (10 g.) was refluxed for 20 minutes with sodium hydroxide (2.5 N, 50 c.c.), and the solution treated with excess of ammonium chloride. The amine, thus obtained, crystallised from boiling alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 163°. (Found : N, 9.3. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.27 per cent). The hydrochloride which turned red on keeping, crystallised from hot hydrochloric acid (10%) in silky plates, m.p. 204-6° (decomp.). (Found : Cl, 10.3. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2ClS$ requires Cl, 10.49 per cent).

N-Benzoyl-β-(4-aminophenyl)-ethylamine, required for the following experiments, was conveniently prepared from the corresponding nitro compound by reduction with sodium sulphide (*cf.* Barger and Walpole, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1722). The nitro compound (24.6 g.), dissolved in hot alcohol, was gradually treated with a concentrated aqueous solution of sodium sulphide crystals (27 g.) and the mixture refluxed for 3 hours on a steam-bath. After removal of alcohol and dilution with water, the separated solid was collected, washed with water and twice crystallised from ethyl acetate, yield 20 g. of pure product.

N¹-(4-β-Benzoylaminoethylphenyl)-acetylsulphanilamide was obtained from the above amine using pyridine as a condensing agent. The product was washed free of pyridine and crystallised from alcohol. The acetylbenzoyl compound separated in fine crystals, m.p. 198-200°. (Found : N, 9.8. $C_{23}H_{23}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 9.61 per cent).

N¹-(4-β-Aminoethylphenyl)-sulphanilamide.—The above derivative (15 g.) was heated for a short time with sodium hydroxide solution (2.5 N, 50 c.c.) when a clear solution resulted. The hot liquid gradually deposited shining leaflets of the sodium derivative of the diamine. It was collected and decomposed by adding an aqueous solution of ammonium chloride. The precipitated solid was crystallised by dissolving in hot pyridine and diluting with hot alcohol. The diamine separated in rosettes of slender silky plates, m.p. 243°. (Found : N, 14.4. $C_{14}H_{17}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 14.42 per cent). The dihydrochloride decomposed at about 210°. The diacetyl derivative, prepared in the usual way, crystallised from alcohol in shining silky prismatic plates, m.p. 223°. (Found : N,* 11.2. $C_{18}H_{21}O_4N_3S$ requires N, 11.2 per cent).

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